

ENHANCING SELF-ESTEEM AND OPTIMISM BASED ON FLIPPED CLASSROOM GUIDANCE ON UNDERGRADUATE COUNSELING STUDENT IN INDONESIA

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Abstract:

The counselor is a helping profession that is required to have an effective personality character, including self-esteem and optimism. The purpose of this study is to increase prospective counselor students' self-esteem and optimism in using flip classroom guidance with animated video media. The experimental design in this study was One Group Pre-test Post-Test. The research subjects were 14 students chosen by random assignment. The instruments used were the Roosenberg Self-Esteem Scale ($\alpha=0,90$) and POSO-E Scale ($\alpha=0,78-0,87$). The results of the t-test showed significant differences in optimism ($t(14) = -5,76, p < 0,05$) and self-esteem ($t(14) = -3,10, p < 0,05$), self-esteem and optimism have a positive correlation ($r = 0,792, p < 0,01$). The flip classroom guidance method with animated video media has proven effective in increasing self-esteem and optimism of prospective counselor students.

Keywords: flip, classroom guidance, self-esteem, optimism

1. Introduction

Counselors are parts of helping profession who must have effective personal qualities. Counselors as helper use themselves as a therapeutic tool for changes in the counselee. Blocher (Ismail et al, 2017) states that personality, values, and interpersonal style of a counselor are important elements in the world of counseling. Gilliland et al (Ismail et al, 2017) state that the most important element in the counseling process is the counselor himself. It shows that who and how the counselor is very important. In line with this, Amla, et al. (2006) suggest that counselors can provide more effective services to clients

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if they have good psychological health and are not bothered by their own uncontrolled problems. Therefore, prospective counselor students must be able to develop aspects related to psychological health including self-acceptance (Ryff, 1989) which is related to how individuals value themselves.

Self-esteem is one of the most important aspects of a person's personality that can shape identity and influence all life. Self-esteem is defined as an assessment made and managed by individuals about themselves (Hutz, 2014; Aryana, 2010; Rosenberg, 1965). This relates to the attitude of agreeing or disagreeing about themselves and showing the extent to which individuals believe in themselves, in their abilities, and achievements. It is important for prospective counselors to develop their self-esteem.

A person who has high self-esteem will increase the probability of success, reduce the effect of failure, and thus develop optimism (Bastianello, 2014; Campbell, Chew, & Scratchley, 1991). This is related to one aspect of the psychological health of a counselor, which is purpose in life, about their career goals which includes targets and goals in counseling (Ismail, Jamaluddin & Sumari, 2017). How a counselor puts positive expectations about the goal in counseling manifests in optimism.

Optimism is a construct of various sides that has been defined in a variety of ways in the empirical literature as positive expectations for the future (Scheier & Carver, 1985), positive inference styles (Peterson & Seligman, 1984), trust in personal control (Alloy & Abramson, 1979), and relative self-improvement view to others (Weinstein, 1980). One of the more prominent characteristics of optimism is positive expectations for the future (Carver & Scheier, 2014; Scheier & Carver, 1985), or the relatively stable expectation that someone will experience favorable outcomes rather than those that are not profitable in the future. The nature of optimism is important to be developed by counselors in carrying out their profession.

More optimistic counselors are less likely to experience compassion fatigue than their less optimistic colleagues (Injeyan et al, 2011), less experience of depression (Kleiman, et al, 2017; Kapikiran & Acun, 2016) and minimize arising depression symptoms (Chang, et al, 2016) and are able to help individuals to face environmental demands (eg., Katz, 1960). Optimism is also known to be the best predictor of life satisfaction (Cabras & Mondo, 2017). A positive relationship is found between optimism and self-esteem. Self-esteem is positively influenced by good expectations for the future. Studies that examine the relationship between optimism and self-esteem in students find a positive relationship (eg Bastianello, Pacico, & Hutz, 2014; Bosson, Brown, & Zeigler-Hill, 2003).

However, researches focusing on factors related to students find that low self-esteem and low optimism as the strongest predictors of stress symptoms (Bhattacharjee & Deb, 2007; Manani Sharma, 2013; Leary, 2004; Rezaei, 2015) and there is a relationship between low self-esteem and low optimism toward anxiety and depression in students (Saleh et al, 2017, Rezaei, 2015). Roman, Cuestas, Dan Fenollar (2008) who analyze the factors that influence academic results find that self-esteem has the strongest impact on learning and increasing self-esteem charge and optimism is very important (Bauman, 2012).

Various literature reveals, how the problems of self-esteem, optimism and emotional matters in individuals including effective counselors/prospective counselors are enhanced by classical structured or group structured experience preparation activities designed and implemented systematically in order to effective self-adjustment abilities in accordance with the stages and developmental tasks (Gysberg, Norman C & Patricia Hernderson, 2006; Stringer, Suzanne, 2003; Morton, 2013; Akos, 2007). Therefore, further services can be carried out with many methods, under the rapid technology development; the application of classroom guidance service method can be combined through the use of technology, namely the flipped classroom method (Daigle, 2016)

Flipped classroom can be considered an educational technique consisting of two parts: interactive group learning activities in the classroom, and direct computer-based individual instruction outside the classroom (Bishop & Verleger, 2013). Caffarella and Daffron (in Moran, 2015) show that adults learn primarily through experience and reflection. Interactive learning opportunities related to the flipped classroom approach are in line with the learning needs of adult experience, especially with the needs of students in counselor education (Moran, 2015). In fact, Osborn and Costas (2013) recommend the use of active learning strategies, such as role playing, to improve overall students' performance in counseling. The method of flipped classroom allows students to develop various materials that they can use in their future practices (Moran, 2015).

The advantages of the flipped classroom method relate to identifying and adapting the learning needs of students individually (Moran, 2015). The method of flipped classroom can facilitate teaching strategies and student-focused services, namely using question-based and problem-based methods, by optimizing time in the classroom mengoptimalkan waktu di dalam kelas (Sergis et al., 2017).

In general, the use of flip classroom method requires preparation of online lectures using audio and video formats as a means of delivering materials. Furthermore, students are asked to review and study the material given before attending class. So that it can encourage students to complete the information management part of learning before entering the classroom (Phillips dan Trainor, 2014). The method of flip classroom will not run well if it does not have a material that is packaged in the form of interesting content, so in this case, the selected content is to use online video, in which it has been revealed in previous studies that in the past few years, there has been growth in learning using online video (Giannakos, 2013). Video is time-based media and contains visual elements that are often combined with other media elements to present content. Furthermore, videos have characteristics including moving images, visualization with audio support which is very suitable for digital animation research (Yuen, M., C. et al., 2018).

Seeing that, there are still few studies that discuss the use of flipped classroom method, especially in the education of prospective counselors. Thus, the purpose of writing this article is to increase self-esteem and optimism of prospective counselors

that can be useful to go through the college process and life in general by utilizing android-based online videos.

2. Method

This experimental study used the research design of one group pretest-posttest. The respondents in this study are 14 Guidance and Counseling students of Semarang State University who were randomly selected (random assignment). The material for the intervention used in this study is in the form of animated videos related to self-esteem and optimism that are equipped with several self-reflection questions and presented in an android-based application, Edmodo, which lasts about four minutes. The material was given two days before direct meeting in class with the research subjects. The discussion of the material was carried out in the class meeting for 45 minutes.

The research data collection instruments used Personal Optimism and Social Optimism-Extended (POSO-E) and Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (Schweizer & Koch, 2000; Rosenberg, 1989) which was adapted using the back translate process. POSO-E contains 10 items of questions from the self-optimism construct ("I will find a solution in every problem"), social optimism ("I master the difficult problem) and self-efficacy ("I gladly accept every new challenge"). The instrument rating is in the form of Likert scale, in which all of them are favorable with four choices of answers ranging from very appropriate to very inappropriate. Instrument reliability ranges from 0,78 to 0,87.

The self-esteem scale contains 10 items of questions from the self-competence construct ("I feel that I have good quality") and self-understanding ("Overall, I am satisfied with myself"). The instrument rating is in the form of Likert scale, in which there are questions that are of favorable value and some are unfavorable with four choices of answers ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The instrument reliability is 0,90 while the validity is 0,71. The data analysis technique is done by using a T-test to find out the differences before and after treatment and a Correlation Test to find out the relationship between optimism and self-esteem, both of which using the version 23 of Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS).

3. Results

There are several things that will be done based on the results of the study including; First, the results of descriptive quantitative analysis of optimism levels and students' self-esteem before getting the treatment. Second, the level of self-esteem and optimism of students after being given the treatment. Third, the results of the *t-test* hypothesis analysis. The last one, the correlation test between self-esteem and optimism.

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that the total average value of the subjects (N=14) before being given intervention in the self-esteem variable in each indicator are; self-competence (M= 15.57 SD= 1.98), self-understanding (M= 12.57 SD= 1.74) and optimism variable in each indicator are; self-optimism (M= 8.86 SD= 1.23), social optimism (M= 7.71 SD= 1.20), and self-efficacy (M= 11.86 SD= 1.87). After giving the intervention, an

increase is experienced and the average total value of the subject (N=14) on the self-esteem variable in each indicator are obtained; self-competence (M= 16.57 SD= 2.31), self-understanding (M= 13.64 SD= 1.82) and optimism variable in each indicator are; self-optimism (M= 10.21 SD= 1.25), social optimism (M= 9.14 SD= 1.23), and self-efficacy (M= 13.50 SD= 2.02).

Table 1: The Results of Pre-test, Post-test and t-test

Variable	Pretest		Posttest		t	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Self-esteem						
Self-Competency	15.57	1.98	16.57	2.31	-2.24	<0.05
Self-understanding	12.57	1.74	13.64	1.82	-2.51	<0.05
Optimism						
Self-Optimism	8.86	1.23	10.21	1.25	-5.46	<0.05
Social Optimism	7.71	1.20	9.14	1.23	-4.90	<0.05
Self-Efficacy	11.86	1.87	13.50	2.02	-3.96	<0.05

Furthermore, the results of hypothesis testing using a *t-test* assisted by SPSS application version 23. Table 1 shows that the results of the *t-test* showed significant differences on the self-esteem variable in each indicator; self-competence ($t(14) = -2.24, p < 0.05$), self-understanding ($t(14) = -2.51, p < 0.05$) and on optimism variable in each indicator; self-optimism ($t(14) = -5.46, p < 0.05$), social optimism ($t(14) = -4.90, p < 0.05$), self-efficacy ($t(14) = -3.96, p < 0.05$). These results indicate that the use of animation-based *flip classroom guidance* method increases self-esteem and optimism on prospective counselor students. In addition to testing the effectiveness of the experimental results, in order to see how the relationship between self-esteem and optimism related, a correlation test was conducted. It is based on a correlation test with *Pearson product-moment* test assisted by SPSS application. Table 2 shows that self-esteem and optimism are positively related. Correlation between self-esteem and optimism is ($r = 0,792, p < 0,01$). There is a positive correlation between self-esteem and optimism.

Table 2: The Results of Pearson Product-Moment test

Variable	N	Pearson Correlation		Criteria
		Self-esteem	Optimism	
Self-esteem	14	0,729"	1	Significant $p < 0,01$
Optimism	14	1	0,792"	

4. Discussion

The results showed that before the intervention was given, the level of self-esteem on prospective counselor students was in the average category. This is shown when students were asked to think about themselves, most students focused on the lack of self rather than the advantages that they have. This finding is in line with the results of Amin (2018) and Durmus (2014) who showed that self-esteem has a correlation with self-confidence. Self-esteem is an important thing that must be owned by prospective

counselors. A person who has a high self-esteem will increase the probability of success, reduce the effect of failure, and thus develop optimism (Bastianello, 2014; Campbell, Chew, & Scratchley, 1991). Thus, it is understood that self-esteem affects one's optimism. In line with that, the findings before the intervention given showed an optimism level of prospective counselor in the medium category. This can be seen in the lack of positive expectations related to the future; in this case, it is related to the expectations of the academic results' value that will be achieved by the students themselves. One form of optimism is shown by having good expectations about the future that also play an important role in adaptation to traumatic or stressful situations, especially in the academic environment (Molinero, 2018).

The results of the t-test showed a significant difference in self-esteem and optimism after the intervention. This is indicated by an increase in the average score of self-esteem and optimism of prospective counselors after the intervention. High self-esteem is indicated by confidence in their ability to be able to complete academic tasks. This relates to the attitude of agreeing or disagreeing about themselves and showing the extent to which individuals believe in themselves, in their abilities, and achievements (Hutz, 2014; Aryana, 2010; Rosenberg, 1965). Prospective counselors have high optimism as indicated by positive beliefs about their future careers. It relates to one aspect of the psychological health of a counselor, which is purpose in life, about their career goals which includes targets and goals in counseling (Ismail, Jamaluddin & Sumari, 2017).

Significant increase in self-esteem optimism of prospective counselors is seen after the intervention using animated-based flip classroom guidance. Some of the things that support the success of the interventions include the use of information and communication technology, especially smart phone in learning, the flexibility of study time and material provided with interesting video format (Roehl, et al., 2013; Strayer; 2008; Bishop & Verleger, 2013; Shahzad, 2012). However, this makes the importance of preparation in learning; both in terms of material and application that are based on android (eg Edmodo) must be well prepared. In line with the opinion of Roehl et al. (2013) that challenges with the flip classroom model include adapting traditional lectures to alternative media to post content online. The introduction and the use of media/application used in flip classroom is another important aspect to be considered, so students get used to and feel comfortable when given the material and in the learning process. This is in line with the opinion of Roehl et al. (2013) that students who participate in flip classroom do not quickly adjust to their new learning environment. As the technology used to present information becomes smarter, faster, better, and cheaper, educators are also forced to learn and access more about media in flip classroom (Prensky, 2010).

This study also found some interesting things. The results of the significant analysis on the self-esteem variable consisting of two predictors, namely self-competence and self-liking showed that not all predictors experienced a significant increase after the intervention. The increase is only shown by predictors of self-liking. This shows that the predictors of self-liking influence the self-esteem of prospective

students counselors. It is also seen in the optimism variables in which from the three predictors, namely self-optimism, social optimism and self-efficacy, predictors of self-efficacy did not experience significant changes.

Correlation test results show that there is a significant relationship between self-esteem and optimism. It can be said that there is a reciprocal relationship between self-esteem and optimism. This can be seen on the prospective counselors who have confidence in their ability also have positive expectations about their future careers. In line with the research done by Myers & Reynolds, (2000) which states that there is positive relationship between self-esteem and optimism that a person has. In line with this, other studies also show the same result that there is a positive relationship between optimism and self-esteem in students (eg Bastianello, Pacico, & Hutz, 2014; Bosson, Brown, & Zeigler-Hill, 2003). This finding reinforces the results of previous studies regarding the relationship between self-esteem and optimism.

5. Conclusion

This study shows that before the intervention was given, the level of self-esteem and optimism in prospective counselor students is still lacking. Through an interview in the form of a flipped classroom guidance method with animation video media, it was proven to be able to increase self-esteem and optimism on prospective counselor students. Self-esteem and optimism are proven to have a positive correlation between each other. The limitations of this study exist in a relatively small number of subjects, and are only limited to female gender. Future research can explore the use of flipped classroom methods in other variables related to education for prospective counselors. Research with more diverse subjects is recommended for future research. The use of other media and more comprehensive material that can be combined with the flip classroom method is also recommended to obtain more optimal results.

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